

Examining Japanese Feminist Ethics Considering Princess Mako's Decision

Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Department of Physics, College of Science, University of the Philippines Baguio, Governor Pack Road, Baguio City, Philippines 2600

mbermundo@up.edu.ph

Abstract

Japan, having a prosperous country and a rich culture, is no stranger to uncanny regulations in terms of the leading family, or the monarch, which is still prevalent nowadays. This paper is an attempt to showcase the ethics of the Japanese royal family and the ideology and struggle of feminism in Japan in light of the decision of one of the princesses of the current monarch, Princess Mako, to be defected in a position to the throne to allow herself to marry the love of her life which she met in college. In addition, I will also try to pinpoint some key details in the concept of feminism in the country.

Keywords: *Japanese monarchy, Japanese ethics, Princess Mako, feminism*

1. Introduction

The wedding of Princess Mako of Japan to his husband, Kei Komuro, meant that she will give up her royal status to marry a commoner under the strict rules of the Imperial Household Law, which it is stated that the females of the royal family who will tie the knot to a non-blue blood will lose their status to ascend to the throne, as also stated in Articles 1 and 2 of Chapter 1 in Japan's national constitution that was passed during the Shōwa era on 1947.¹ Even before being married to Komuro, the engaged couple has been under the extreme scrutiny of the media and critics, with some telling out that her soon-to-be husband during that time was not good enough for Princess Mako as details on a financial scandal by which the mother of Komuro is involved in this controversy.^{2,3}

These series of opinions and statements have also been affected the well-being of the couple, with Princess Mako being reported to be diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder because of the negative interactions that are found on the internet.⁴ Since the announcement of Princess Mako's engagement to the media in 2017, their couple is also likened to the British royal family, as they are also dubbed as "Japan's Harry and Meghan".⁵ However, the princess remained faithful to her love, as she said, "For me, Kei is irreplaceable — marriage was a necessary choice for us."⁶

While the imperial family of Japan has been keeping up with the modernization of their country as well as tackling and analyzing certain aspects of their leadership, there still has a lot of laws in the royal household that are being preserved and backed on by traditionalists of the royalty of the throne. Especially for now, as there are only a few male members in the clan that are eligible to take over to the throne in case the emperor wants to abstain itself or die due to an illness or old age.

One good example for the revisioning of the legislations of the royal family is the protocol which dictated that women in the royal household had to walk a few steps behind the male members

of the household, which has been long disregarded as it is not applicable in today's standards.⁷ However, the conventional rules that the imperial family remains bounded by are that of the rules that signify their status as royals, such as the case of the Imperial Household Law of 1947, one of which is that the female members of the family who marry commoners will lose their royal status.⁸ This law has been the one that Princess Mako and Kei Komuro abided to in the name of the royal family.

But Princess Mako is not the first one to abide the law because of marrying a commoner in Japan. In 2005, her aunt Sayako (Princess Nori) married a man named Yoshiki Kuroda, an urban town planner and a government official.^{9, 10} However, the first account for a female member of the Japanese royal family to get married was Empress Emerita Michiko to Emperor Emeritus Akihito in the year 1959, which also became a symbol of Japan's modernization.^{11, 12}

1 ("THE CONSTITUTION OF JAPAN" 2013)

2 ("Komuro Settles Mother's Money Trouble | NHK WORLD-JAPAN News" 2021)

3 ("PressReader.Com - Digital Newspaper & Magazine Subscriptions" 2021)

4 (Reuters 2021)

5 ("The 'Meghan and Harry of Japan', Princess Mako and Kei Komuro Prepare Their Wedding" 2021)

6 (BBC News 2021)

7 ("Now That Princess Mako Has Married and Left the Royal Life, She May Finally Be Left Alone" 2021)

8 (Pearl 2018)

9 ("Princess Nori of Japan Begins New Life as Plain Mrs Kuroda" 2005)

10 ("Japanese Princess Trades Palace for Apartment" 2005)

11 ("JAPAN: The Girl from Outside - TIME" 2009)

12 (NEWS 2019)13 Keiko Mukai, "Nation in Production: Japanese Royal Wedding in the Media," Spectrum Research Repository (Concordia University, 1994), <https://spectrum.library.concordia.ca/id/eprint/3750/1/MM01308.pdf>.

2. Ethics in the Japanese Royal Family

To start off the study of the ethics of the imperial Japanese family, I would like to explain first the identity of Japan as a nation, that was detailed in the paper of Kukai in 1994. In his paper, he discusses the context of "Japaneseness" or *Nihonjinron*. In particular, he says that approach of this topic by explaining the gist of mutual dependence or *amae*, and a belief of a classless society or *mukaikyuu shinkai*.¹³ As a particular example for his explanation is the work of Doi in 1971 which suggests that *amae*, being a term that has no direct translation like *eudaimonia*, is a cluster of constructions in a psychoanalytic context such as being dependent, passive, or being separated.¹⁴ In contrast, he presents the argument of Umesao in his work about the determinism of the Japanese in 1990, where it is asserted that the classlessness of the people living in Japan is due to the restoration during the *Meiji* period where classes are nullified to an extent that it is hard to differentiate the living conditions in urban and rural areas due to the rapid adaptation to technologies to that country during that period.¹⁵ While being criticized for how this ideology is intermediated from the mixture of Japanese and Western notions, they tell an aspect on how the Japanese evolved as a society that they are now in the modern day.

Kukai then proposes and argument by which the idea of *Nihonjinron* in particular presented paradoxes that are overviewed by those that who studied it earlier on and just focused on how the nation is unique to other nations, specifically those that are on the Western part of the world. This also allowed the said idea to be debunked by critics as it doesn't present itself on how individuals in Japan would be analyzed, but rather the stereotypical nature of the culture itself. To understand this paradox, Kukai presents us with the propositions of Nakane (1990) that tells that the society of Japan is based on the groups of institutions in the country and not by the regular structure that is

found in other civilizations that emerged.¹⁶ This was supported by Hamaguchi in 1980 where it is pointed out that the lack of being individualistic in the people of Japan shows that there is a factor of consideration amongst other people. This type of culture in Japan shows their aspect of them being unique in an interpersonal manner.¹⁷

In relation, a report entitled, “Age of Culture” by the prime minister Masayoshi Ohira during his time (1978-1980) tells that the people of Japan sticks out on having interpersonal relationships towards other people and that other cultures, specifically that of Western cultures, is reliant to their individualism and as a society, works out through the frameworks of it. Adding to the results of the said report, the interpersonal connections presume a society that is based on the perception of *nakama* or a group society and that of an *ie* or a family society.¹⁸ In the interim another council in Japan named as the Ad Hoc Council points out that being individualistic in Japan is just as important as the relationships that are mentioned in the report of prime minister Ohira during his mandate.¹⁹

Now that we know how the culture of Japan primarily works, we must delve into the history of the current imperial household, so that this paper will not be covering the feudal history of the country and will be covering only the events that occurred during the restoration during the *Meiji* period. But how do the events that transpired in the same period become crucial to the modern ethics of the Japanese people, particularly in the current royal family of the country?

When the *Edo* period from 1600 to 1867 generally allowed the country to be exposed to new ventures by the Western colonizers as well as the struggle for change in the society as a whole, the construction of the period during *Meiji* became political as the emperor embraced the call for the country to be modernized with the continuous decay of the system of feudal lords to fit into the mix of the country being open to the doors of foreign people. Along with this is the movement of being democratic, as the former vassals and the bourgeoisie were not pleased enough with the movement that is happening in the country. However, after a series of heated arguments regarding the matter, the government during that time proposed a parliament that will be open to the public that will be led by who is the current emperor. With this out of the way, the imperial household have made a constitution in the name of the emperor, by which only he is the central figurehead of the country and is the absolute leader that is in charge with the responsibilities of leadership, as well as having the advantage of the emperor on the throne being having inviolable activity as it was stated in the constitution. To further elaborate, the position that the emperor holds has a legitimacy that is legalized by the Imperial Household of Japan.

The emperor in that case has attained the highest power even after modernizing primarily due to three reasons. The first reason is that it is summoned as it naturalizes the interests of new authority, or a construction of a "modern" emperor system that is involved with the legitimacy of new authority and a new look that has a focal point of identifying itself as a symbol of the modernization of the country. The second reason is that it is under a familiar narrative of a father figure as the connotation of historical continuity and authentication of a nation that is supposed to be now reborn are constituted around the ideas that are familiar to them such as the narratives of patriarchy - the father as the head of the *ie* or family through the manifestation of what of what the emperor represents to a modern Japan. The final reason is that of state capitalism and how Japan acted towards it, as they are considered to be a late bloomer in being industrialized. As there is a need for an industrialization that is being sponsored by the state, then the state must have that strongman figure to support the needs of the nation.

These symbolisms for the power of the royal family was then translated to the population of Japan through the usage of mass media. The country has focused itself on the control of media as a means of securing the political awareness of the emerging generation of the Japanese community via promotion of the emperor's power and through the modernization and the uprising of a new country. This trend is also seen in Johnson's paper in 1975, with the national newspapers of Japan that emerged in the country in 1879 usually emphasizes on the information all around the country that is relevant to the people on their local surroundings.²⁰ It also revolutionized the way of delivering the information in the country as it breaks free from the influence of other parties and instead focus on the goal of bringing national issues and happenings. In radios, the same can also be said as the government of Japan prioritized the regularization of media through the wireless telegraphy law of 1915.^{21, 22} Japan had positioned broadcasting and other forms of media as vital to the program of "publicity and information" in the country.^{23, 24}

However, things changed for the emperor as well as the royal family after the defeat in the second world war, where the emperor is now more presented in a humane manner, where he is always surrounded by his family members. But Japanese scholars have pointed out that the emperor (and by extension, the royal family), garnered attention to the public as they now show the changes and a great movement or the future of the country, which is backed up by the overexaggerating activities of mass media.^{25, 26} This, in a way, allowed the enthronement of the royal family and all of its events or legislations to be taken seriously, as noted by scholars that explored topic in regards to the authority of the Chrysanthemum Throne.^{27, 28, 29} Generally speaking, the imperial family have undergone massive changes to keep up with other nations, specifically Western countries, and at one point perceived its rule to be superior, only to be humanized after the world established and moved forward to a more peaceful way of dealing things out and keeping every man in the world to be a free man.

13 (Mukai 1994)

14 (Doi and Bester 2010)

15 (Umesao 1990)

16 (Goodman 1991)

17 (Esyun, Shumpei, and Creighton 1985)

18 (Takeuchi 2006)

19 ("JAPANESE GOVERNMENT POLICIES IN EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND CULTURE 1989" n.d.)

20 (Johnson 1975)

21 ("Overview | Radio Law | Mandatory Approvals | Testing and Certification of Electrical and Electronic Products | JQA" n.d.)

22 ("MIC The Radio Use Website | Conformity Certification System | Technical Regulations Conformity Certification System" n.d.)

23 (Brown and Yamashita 1995)

24 (W.G.B 1956)

25 (Matsushita 1988)

26 (Dayan and Katz 1992)

27 (Befu 2001)

28 (Lock, 1988)

29 (Armason 1988)

3. A Bold Move for Feminism in Japan

Feminism in Japan is always a special case, as they are always exploring topics that are in and out of the comfort zone of the public. But how did it start? In the years from 1868 to 1898, following the Meiji Restoration, factory labor was a common norm for Japanese women. However, others can be seen in red light districts, with their earnings being significant to the country as they bring in

foreign money. During these times, Japan was a constitutional monarchy and some rights, especially for that of women severely limited. But the writings of Rousseau, Mill and Spencer gave way for the theorization of feminism in Japan.³⁰ In the Meiji Constitution, individual rights and duties are placed to the subject to the Emperor's power and 'natural rights' for women were not almost recognized as Japan at that time is a state that do not distinguish such concepts.^{31, 32} The Civil Code of 1898 introduced a number of laws which placed women in a patriarchal basis, as married women had no political rights no claims over property that were brought during marriage.³³ This family structure was presented as conventional for the Japanese standards, yet it was actually bought in as a burden of the feudal systems in the country before being modernized.

Female ideologies in the family, particularly the concept of *ryosai kenbo*, or the concept of women being "good wives and wise mothers", which is a mixture of Confucian and Western ideas that was developed to denote the significance of mothers as the first teachers of their children.³⁴ In the year 1872, the requirement for all boys and girls to be educated was made compulsory by the government, but much of women's schooling in these schools were designed to fit them into the roles of wife and mother in the future. The early schools that were intended for women are found in mission schools that introduced and disseminate the ideas of "separate spheres" and romantic love in marriage. Although private women's colleges and medical schools were founded for women to enter in their education, it would take years before women could attend national universities in the country.

Societies that are philanthropic in nature and uphold a traditional view of women's role such as the Red Cross and the Japanese chapter of the Women's Christian Temperance Union that were established in the 1880's brought women into the contact with the situation of factory workers, prostitutes and other working women and presented the argument for this to be better. These societies actually belonged to the few socially sanctioned ways for middle-class women to engage in activities outside the home and these groups also supported women's political rights and demanded an end to concubinage and promoted monogamy male sexual behavior reforms to solve the underlying health problems that are brought by such activities.^{35,36} These were done by campaigned against prostitution or the cases of *karayuki-san* in other Asian countries and this was followed by the formation of the first patriotic women's organization named as *Aikoku Fujin Kai* in 1901 mobilized conservative women into support for militarism.^{37,38}

Fast forward to the current times and now researchers are progressing to examine the role of women in the national mobilization of the 1940's to see if women during those times are seen as active participants in this process of mobilization in Japan.³⁹ If this was proven to be true then feminist historians will be able to draw and possibly expose that root causes and effects of ideological pressures which women of Japan of the current time were now seeing upon themselves. Also, interests for rediscovering feminist activism in Japan has been widely explored and considered to look at the history of it. This movement has been initiated through looking at the many pioneers of the feminist movement in Japan such as Hiratsuka Raicho, Yamakawa Kikue, and Takamure Itsue.^{40, 41} These rediscoveries and reexaminations of these feminist women in Japan could also bring way to study in-depth and also put into exposition the philosophical strengths and weaknesses of their arguments to give contributions towards the failure of pre-war feminism to oppose on the militaristic views of the Japanese government during the 1930's. A reappraisal of family history may also challenge the myth of the 'unique Japanese family system' which has so often been used to justify women's relegation to the domestic sphere.

In the case of the royal women, they often have more benefits than the common Japanese woman due to their heredity and their connections to the throne. As the Imperial Throne has been succeeded by the concept of ancient heredity and is also closely related to role of the leading emperor as *maturinushi* or a priest who conducts rituals. Considering that this is the fact that directs the ultimate legitimacy of the emperor which comes from an ancient concept, the concept of maternal lineage doesn't exist, and the leader of that bloodline was exclusively dependent on the paternal lines of the clan. ^{42, 43}

However, the talk that is now relevant in these current times is the popular discussion today is to establish a house of an imperial princess that married outside the clan and their child can succeed to the Imperial Throne. From the popular view, this is now being considered and is relevant as it doesn't completely destroy the ancient rule in Japan, but it gives way for transitioning another paternal line that is related to the early imperial line. The only problem in this is that some will consider it as impure. However, with the recent situations in the lineage of the throne, this could be another way to continue the modernization of the Japanese imperial family. ^{44, 45}

While women in the imperial household doesn't exhibit the same problems as that of common Japanese women, they still are under the problems of the ancient traditions of Japan that prioritizes the lineage of the males and disregard some rights of the women in their household. However, the modernization of the country is also progressive and has reached some of it to the royal clan. Should an emergence of a situation of the emperor line being wiped out as there is no male to succeed, will the country accept the role of women in order to continue the line with the wedding of some of the women in the family to commoners? If so, this will bring a change to the societal norms of Japan and thus bring a win for feminism in country. ^{46, 47, 48}

30 (Macciocchi 1979)

31 ("1889 Japanese Constitution" n.d.)

32 (Mackie 1988)

33 ("Meiji Reforms - Kishida Toshiko, (1863-1901) - Japan - Primary Source" n.d.)

34 (Mackie 1988)

35 (Robins-Mowry and Reischauer, n.d.)

36 (Bulbeck 1991)

37 (Morishima 2008)

38 (Caldicott 1982)

39 (Garon 1993)

40 (Mackie 1988)

41 (Kuninobu 1984)

42 (CNN n.d.)

43 ("Lacking the Royal Y Chromosome - Taipei Times" 2005)

44 ("FOCUS: Imperial Succession Issue behind Recent Talks on Female Members' Status. - Free Online Library" n.d.)

45 ("Report: Japan to Drop Plan to Allow Female Monarch - USATODAY.Com" n.d.)

46 (Tokyo n.d.)

47 (Mainichi Daily News 2020)

48 (NEWS n.d.)

4. Conclusions

In this current age of globalization, numerous opportunities to expand the nature of human learning have multiplied, and in this paper, I showed how such an orderly and disciplined society like Japan act upon the case of their own brand of feminism. The ideology behind feminist ethics in the country could also be attributed to the individual integrity, sense of shame, and cases of immorality

amongst its male citizens. The use of Japanese culture as a subject is not equivalent to disregard for cultural differences and unique historical background on other cultures, especially in their own case of feminism. Regardless of our nationality, each of us has a profound opportunity to reflect on our culture and society, to learn on what should we improve, as persons, as we continue to expand our consciousness on the notion of treating males and females of our society as the same on what they are capable of.

By exploring the gist of what is the motive of feminism in the country, one can see that there are both positive and negative lessons to be learned from a consideration of feminist politics in Japan. The whole experience of Japanese women can be seen as a rally against the naive faith in legislation that doesn't recognize programs for action and support for women workers in the form of adequate welfare services for both women and children. In a country where fewer than women held lower editorial positions than men, action are taken in a grassroots level and as such, the movement of women in the royal family as commoners leads to two possible situations: one where the remaining younger men in the family will preserve the heritage or one with the re-acceptance of the women members of the family to take over for a while the spot of the emperor.

What distinguishes the various relationships however will be determined by the activity of interaction with others. In the case of Japan, it seems that the idea of feminism there is to uphold the same values of men there with women. However, with the case of the current royal family, the decision for having the next emperor seems bleak as there is only one remaining member that is eligible to the throne. With Princess Mako tying the knot and with other royal family members not being eligible for the throne, it is to be taken in consideration that an empress should lead the nation soon, or even as a regent or a dowager. The possible distinction of a high status of a woman in power in the near future is an empowering moment for Japanese women, and also a possible step forward for the further modernization of the royal family. This will be a big move if that possibility will happen, and it will require ethical considerations when going further. In this paper, I pinpointed the key points of feminism in the country, as this can be affected with the decision of a close family member to the throne moving out, hence the title of this paper.

References

- “1889 Japanese Constitution.” n.d. Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://history.hanover.edu/texts/1889con.html>.
- “Archive.Md.” n.d. Accessed December 7, 2021. https://archive.md/20140928151842/http://ajw.asahi.com/article/behind_news/politics/AJ201409280017.
- Arnason, Johann. "Paths to modernity: the peculiarities of Japanese feudalism." *Modernization and Beyond: The Japanese Trajectory* (1988): 235-263.
- BBC News. 2021. “Japan’s Princess Mako Finally Marries Commoner Boyfriend Kei Komuro,” October 26, 2021, sec. Asia. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-59046476>.
- Befu, Harumi, and Sylvie Guichard-Anguis, eds. *Globalizing Japan: ethnography of the Japanese presence in Asia, Europe, and America*. Vol. 51. Psychology Press, 2001.

- Brown, James Dean, and Sayoko Okada Yamashita. 1995. *Language Testing in Japan*. JALT Central Office, Urban Edge Bldg. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED400713>.
- Bulbeck, Chilla. 1991. "Hearing the Difference: First and Third World Feminisms." *Asian Studies Review* 15 (1): 77–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03147539108712747>.
- Caldicott, Leonie. "At the Foot of the Mountain: the Shibokusa Women of Mount Fuji!" *Lynn Jones. London* (1982).
- Chapman, David, and Laura Dales. 2006. "Feminisms and Differences in Japan: Korean-Japanese Women's Activism and Japanese Feminisms (OCIS Conference Refereed Proceedings)," January. https://www.academia.edu/11247689/Feminisms_and_differences_in_Japan_Korean_Japanese_women_s_activism_and_Japanese_feminisms_OCIS_Conference_Refereed_Proceedings_.
- Chapman, David, Laura Dales, and Vera Mackie. 2008. "'Minority Women Will Change the World!': Perspectives on Multiple Discrimination in Japan." *Women's Studies International Forum* 31 (3): 192–99. https://www.academia.edu/210274/Minority_Women_Will_Change_the_World_Perspectives_on_Multiple_Discrimination_in_Japan.
- CNN, Juliet Perry and Yoko Wakatsuki. n.d. "Japan: What Happens If the Emperor Steps Down?" CNN. Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://www.cnn.com/2016/07/14/asia/japanese-emperor-abdication/index.html>.
- Dayan, Daniel, and Elihu Katz. *Media events*. harvard university press, 1992.
- Doi, Takeo, and John Bester. *The Anatomy of Dependence*. Tokyo etc.: Kodansha International, 2010.
- Esyun, Hamaguchi, Kumon Shumpei, and Mildred R. Creighton. 1985. "A Contextual Model of the Japanese: Toward a Methodological Innovation in Japan Studies." *Journal of Japanese Studies* 11 (2): 289–321. <https://doi.org/10.2307/132562>.
- Faiz, Ahmad. n.d. "Yoshio Sugimoto an Introduction to Japanese Society." Accessed December 7, 2021. https://www.academia.edu/37346687/Yoshio_sugimoto_an_introduction_to_japanese_society.
- "FOCUS: Imperial Succession Issue behind Recent Talks on Female Members' Status. - Free Online Library." n.d. Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://www.thefreelibrary.com/FOCUS%3A+Imperial+succession+issue+behind+recent+talks+on+female...-a0274125295>.
- Garon, Sheldon. 1993. "Women's Groups and the Japanese State: Contending Approaches to Political Integration, 1890-1945." *Journal of Japanese Studies* 19 (1): 5–41. <https://doi.org/10.2307/132863>.
- Germer, Andrea. 2005. "Hiratsuka Raicho and Early Japanese Feminism (Review)." *Monumenta Nipponica*, January. https://www.academia.edu/1626777/Hiratsuka_Raicho_and_Early_Japanese_Feminism_review_Goodman, Grant K. 1991. "Tokugawa Japan: The Social and Economic Antecedents of Modern Japan. Edited by Chie Nakane and Shinzaburo Oishi. Tokyo: University of Tokyo

- Press, 1990. Viii, 240 Pp.” *The Journal of Asian Studies* 50 (4): 935–36. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2058583>.
- Herdiati, Salsabil. n.d. “Japanese Feminism.” Accessed December 7, 2021. https://www.academia.edu/11224494/Japanese_Feminism.
- Hongo, Jun. 2014. “Obituary: Takako Doi, Japan’s First Female Lower House Speaker.” *Wall Street Journal*, September 29, 2014, sec. Japan Real Time. <https://www.wsj.com/articles/BL-JRTB-18074>.
- “Japan: Shokado Women’s Bookstore.” n.d. *Our Bodies Ourselves* (blog). Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://www.ourbodiesourselves.org/global-projects/japan-shokado-womens-bookstore/>.
- “JAPAN: The Girl from Outside - TIME.” 2009. September 6, 2009. <https://web.archive.org/web/20090906161206/http://www.time.com/time/magazine/article/0,9171,892335-1,00.html>.
- “JAPANESE GOVERNMENT POLICIES IN EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND CULTURE 1989.” n.d. Accessed December 2, 2021. https://www.mext.go.jp/b_menu/hakusho/html/hpae198901/index.html.
- “Japanese Princess Trades Palace for Apartment.” 2005. NBC News. November 15, 2005. <https://www.nbcnews.com/id/wbna10045158>.
- Johnson, Chalmers. 1975. “Japan: Who Governs? An Essay on Official Bureaucracy.” *Journal of Japanese Studies* 2 (1): 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.2307/132037>.
- Kato, Masae. 2009. “Women’s Rights? : The Politics of Eugenic Abortion in Modern Japan.” *IIAS Publication Series*. https://www.academia.edu/28813028/Womens_Rights_The_Politics_of_Eugenic_Abortion_in_Modern_Japan.
- “Komuro Settles Mother’s Money Trouble | NHK WORLD-JAPAN News.” n.d. NHK WORLD. Accessed November 30, 2021. https://www3.nhk.or.jp/nhkworld/en/news/20211113_08/.
- Kuninobu, Junko Wada. 1984. “Women’s Studies in Japan.” *Women’s Studies International Forum* 7 (4): 301–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-5395\(84\)90055-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-5395(84)90055-4).
- “Lacking the Royal Y Chromosome - Taipei Times.” 2005. December 29, 2005. <https://www.taipeitimes.com/News/editorials/archives/2005/12/29/2003286524>.
- Lie, John. 2001. *Multiethnic Japan*. https://www.academia.edu/2128782/Multiethnic_Japan.
- Lock, Margaret. "A nation at risk: interpretations of school refusal in Japan." In *Biomedicine examined*, pp. 377-414. Springer, Dordrecht, 1988.
- Macciocchi, Maria-Antonietta. 1979. “Female Sexuality in Fascist Ideology.” *Feminist Review* 1 (1): 67–82. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.1979.6>.
- Mackie, Vera. 1988. “Feminist Politics in Japan.” *New Left Review*, January. https://www.academia.edu/605969/Feminist_Politics_in_Japan.

- Mackie, Vera. 1988. "Dialogue, Distance and Difference." *Women's Studies International Forum* 21 (6): 599–615. https://www.academia.edu/605975/Dialogue_Distance_and_Difference_Feminism_in_contemporary_japan.
- Mainichi Daily News*. 2020. "Japan Defense Minister Suggests Considering 'matrilineal Emperors' for Stable Succession," August 25, 2020. <https://mainichi.jp/english/articles/20200825/p2a/00m/0na/006000c>.
- Matsushita, Kōnosuke. *Quest for prosperity: the life of a Japanese industrialist*. PHP Institute, 1988.
- "Meiji Reforms - Kishida Toshiko, (1863-1901) - Japan - Primary Source." n.d. Accessed December 7, 2021. <http://womeninworldhistory.com/WR-04.html#:~:text=the%20Meiji%20Civil%20Code%20of%201898%20which%20gave,disapprove%20of%20marriage%20and%20divorce%2C%20and%20control%20inheritance>.
- "MIC The Radio Use Website | Conformity Certification System | Technical Regulations Conformity Certification System." n.d. Accessed December 6, 2021. <https://www.tele.soumu.go.jp/e/sys/equ/tech/index.htm>.
- Morishima, Akira. "Comparative studies on sex workers in Japan, Australia and New Zealand: The way to unionisation of sex workers." *The Otemon Journal of Australian Studies* 34, no. 6 (2008): 55-65.
- Mukai, Keiko. "Nation in Production: Japanese Royal Wedding in the Media." Spectrum Research Repository. Concordia University, 1994. <https://spectrum.library.concordia.ca/id/eprint/3750/1/MM01308.pdf>.
- NEWS, KYODO. 2019. "60 Years in Photos: Japanese Emperor Akihito and Empress Michiko." Kyodo News+. April 10, 2019. <https://english.kyodonews.net/news/2019/04/865274413410-in-photos-japanese-emperor-akihito-empress-michiko-60-years-of-marriage.html>.
- NEWS, KYODO. n.d. "Japan Eyes Post-Marital Title for Female Imperial Family Members." Kyodo News+. Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://english.kyodonews.net/news/2020/11/92dc9ef833c0-japan-eyes-post-marital-title-for-female-imperial-family-members.html>.
- "Now That Princess Mako Has Married and Left the Royal Life, She May Finally Be Left Alone." 2021. The Indian Express (blog). October 28, 2021. <https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/editorials/not-a-fairytale-princess-mako-japan-commoner-kei-komuro-7594182/>.
- "Overview | Radio Law | Mandatory Approvals | Testing and Certification of Electrical and Electronic Products | JQA." n.d. Accessed December 6, 2021. <https://www.jqa.jp/english/safety/service/mandatory/radio/>.
- Pearl, Diana. 2018. "PEOPLE Explains: Why Women In Japan's Imperial Family Must Give Up Their Royal Status to Marry Commoners." PEOPLE.Com. February 7, 2018. <https://people.com/royals/japan-imperial-family-women-give-up-royal-status-marry-commoner-why/>.

- “PressReader.Com - Digital Newspaper & Magazine Subscriptions.” 2021. April 16, 2021. <https://www.pressreader.com/japan/the-japan-news-by-the-yomiuri-shimbun/20210416/281715502441423>.
- “Princess Nori of Japan Begins New Life as Plain Mrs Kuroda.” 2005. *The Independent*. November 16, 2005. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/asia/princess-nori-of-japan-begins-new-life-as-plain-mrs-kuroda-515521.html>.
- “Report: Japan to Drop Plan to Allow Female Monarch - USATODAY.Com.” n.d. Accessed December 7, 2021. https://usatoday30.usatoday.com/money/world/2007-01-03-japan-female-monarch_x.htm.
- Reuters. 2021. “Japan Princess Overcomes Scandal, PTSD to Marry College Sweetheart.” *New York Post* (blog). October 21, 2021. <https://nypost.com/2021/10/21/japan-princess-overcomes-scandal-ptsd-to-marry-sweetheart/>.
- Robins-Mowry, Dorothy, and Edwin O. Reischauer. n.d. *The Hidden Sun: Women of Modern Japan*.
- “Tadao Umesao’s Collection Volume 7 Japanese Studies (Book in Japanese) by Tadao Umesao: Fine Soft Cover (1990) | Yun.” n.d. Accessed December 2, 2021. <https://www.abebooks.co.uk/Tadao-Umesaos-Collection-Volume-Japanese-Studies/31014389858/bd>.
- Takeuchi, Mito. “The Reinforcement of Cultural Nationalism in Japan: An Investigation of Japaneseness and ‘the Notebook for the Heart.’” CORE. CORE. Accessed December 2, 2021. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/129158101.pdf>.
- “The Achievements of Takako Doi.” 2014. *The Japan Times*. October 1, 2014. <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/opinion/2014/10/01/editorials/achievements-takako-doi/>.
- “THE CONSTITUTION OF JAPAN.” 2013. December 14, 2013. https://web.archive.org/web/20131214104438/http://www.kantei.go.jp/foreign/constitution_and_government_of_japan/constitution_e.html.
- “The ‘Meghan and Harry of Japan’, Princess Mako and Kei Komuro Prepare Their Wedding.” 2021. MSN. October 24, 2021. <https://www.msn.com/en-ph/entertainment/news/princess-mako-and-kei-komuro-prepare-to-marry-who-are-the-meghan-and-harry-of-japan/ss-AAPKWtl>.
- Tokyo, Richard Lloyd Parry. n.d. “Adopted Sons Tipped to Stave off Japan’s Imperial Succession Crisis,” sec. world. Accessed December 7, 2021. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/adopted-sons-tipped-to-stave-off-japan-imperial-succession-crisis-m25n8bncv>.
- W.G.B. 1956. “Delmer M. Brown: Nationalism in Japan: An Introductory Historical Analysis. Xi, 336 Pp., Berkeley and Los Angeles: University of California Press, 1955. (English Agents: C.U.P. 37s. 6d.)” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 18 (2): 402–3. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0041977X00107256>.